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MULTI-CRITERIA DECISION-MAKING FOR ROBOT SELECTION BASED ON CROSS-ENTROPY

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Abstract: Due to the fact that there is an increasing number of robots in use, decision-making in the field of robotics is extremely important. Robots are complex machines and their impacts on society are numerous, so multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) is a suitable tool for their selection. The literature about MCDM methods for robot selection is rich, but still, there is a lot of vague, uncertain, and incomplete information in the decision-making processes. Therefore, fuzzy approaches are recognized in addition to standard MCDM methods. This paper suggests the use of cross-entropy in hesitant intuitionistic fuzzy sets (HIFS) environment for performing MCDM procedures for robot selection. Possible applications of cross-entropy for discrete-valued HIFS and for interval-valued HIFS will be presented and illustrated on practical examples to point to the advantages of the suggested approach for solving optimization problems regarding robot selection.

Keywords: Robot Selection, Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM), Cross-Entropy, Hesitant Intuitionistic Fuzzy Sets (HIFS).

1. INTRODUCTION

Robot selection, in relation to the characteristics which best fit necessary requirements, is a critical task (Sen *et al.*, 2015). Decision-makers in the field of robotics should have multidisciplinary knowledge (for example, in professions such as electrical engineering, mechanical engineering, informatics), which is why it is necessary to have multiple criteria when deciding during the selection of robots.

Industrial robots were in the focus in early development (Hudson, 2019), but the use of robots that are not intended for industrial purposes is also widespread in the literature today (for research, educational, medical, rescue, and other activities), as well as on the market. The selection of proper robots is a challenging and risky task, no matter if discussing a robot to be made or to be purchased for some purpose. In the first case, many characteristics need to be considered, improved, or invented for future robot functionalities. In the second one, there is a lot of choice on the market today, but the question is which solution is the best for a given context of use. Cost aspects must also be taken into account, as well as organizational, social, environmental, and ethical impacts.

It is interesting how people that are intuitive beings decide about autonomous technical systems. During robot selection, especially when considering a robot's innovative characteristics, experts are prone to give subjective assessments due to the lack of exact information and the presence of cognitive biases. When they rely on intuition ('gut feeling' factors), some people are inclined to affirmatively vote, some rather prefer disagreement, while the others tend to be reserved due to hesitancy (Wang and Li, 2011). Therefore, three degrees of membership to hesitant intuitionistic fuzzy sets (HIFS) will be considered in this paper, in relation to the level of satisfaction of decision-maker with the offered alternative regarding defined criterion.

MCDM for robot selection is often elaborated by using different methods in the literature: AHP – Analytic Hierarchy Process (Goh, 1997), PROMETHEE II – Preference Ranking Organization METHod for Enrichment Evaluation II (Sen *et al.*, 2015), VIKOR – Višekriterijumsko KOmpromisno Rangiranje (Chatterjee *et al.*, 2010), ELECTRE – ELimination and Et Choice Translating REality (Chatterjee *et al.*, 2010), TOPSIS – Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (Bhangale *et al.*, 2004). However, despite many advantages of these methods and their relatively frequent use in the literature, especially for industrial robot selection, it is questionable how experts vote and how they determine the weight coefficients among criteria. The problem is bigger if decision-makers give numerical estimations at the beginning of the implementation of MCDM procedure, such as in *a priori* approaches (Vujošević, 2012), and when there is no possibility to change them later. This is a common case in practice and real-life situations, where an uncertain environment is a dominant category.

In the process of robot selection, both objective and subjective criteria are recognized in the literature (Parameshwaran *et al*, 2015). In order to deal with uncertainty and subjective judgments for robot selection, many authors integrate MCDM methods with fuzzy set logic, for example: fuzzy AHP (Kapoor and Tak, 2005), IF-VIKOR or extended VIKOR in intuitionistic fuzzy environment (Devi, 2011), fuzzy TOPSIS (Chu and Lin, 2003), IVF-COPRAS or interval-valued fuzzy multiple criteria complex proportional assessment (Vahdani *et al*, 2014). In fuzzy MCDM methods, linguistic terms represented by fuzzy numbers are used for the weight criteria evaluation.

Since entropy is important when measuring uncertain information (Ye, 2009), the approach that will be suggested in this paper is multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) based on cross-entropy. The use of cross-entropy for solving ill-structured MCDM problems for robot selection under HIFS environment will be presented for discrete-valued HIFS in combination with score functions (Wang and Li, 2011), as well as for interval-valued HIFS (Ye, 2011; Narayanamoorthy *et al*, 2019; Ye, 2010) in combination with extended TOPSIS (Zhang and Yu, 2012; Tian *et al*, 2015;). The first case will be illustrated by the example of the selection of an industrial robot and the second one by the example of an education robot. Possible contributions of the suggested approach will be discussed.

2. CROSS-ENTROPY IN MCDM OPTIMIZATION

Cross-entropy is a function of two probability distributions, P or “true” distribution, and Q or predicted distribution. Starting from the standard well-known definition of entropy, $H(P) = -\sum_{i=1}^n p_i \log_2 p_i$, defined under probability distribution $P = \{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n\}$, $p_i \in [0,1]$, $\sum_{i=1}^n p_i = 1$, the cross-entropy between the probability distributions P and Q can be defined as follows (Ye, 2009):

$$H(P, Q) = -\sum_{i=1}^n p_i \log_2 \frac{p_i}{q_i}.$$

The cross-entropy $H(P, Q)$ is always greater or equal to entropy $H(P)$:

- $H(P, Q) > H(P)$, when Q is different than P ,
- $H(P, Q) = H(P)$, when Q is equal to P .

For $n = 2$, when $P = \{p, 1 - p\}$ and $Q = \{q, 1 - q\}$, the binary cross-entropy between the probability distributions P and Q is defined as follows (Ye, 2011):

$$H(P, Q) = p \log_2 \frac{p}{q} + (1 - p) \log_2 \frac{1-p}{1-q}. \quad (1)$$

Decisions should be entirely based on the facts. In reality, when there are insufficiently known and uncertain parameters, decisions also rely on likelihood to some extent. In those situations, decision-makers embed their own intuition in decisions. The motivation for the use of cross-entropy in MCDM optimization under HIFS environment is to grasp this problematics in order to make the right decisions.

2.1. Cross-entropy for discrete-valued HIFS in combination with score functions

If X is a universal set, then a discrete-valued intuitionistic fuzzy set can be defined as (Yao and Wang, 2018):

$$I = \{x, \mu_I(x), \nu_I(x) | x \in X\},$$

where $\mu_I: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ and $\nu_I: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ represent the degree of membership and the degree of non-membership respectively, i.e. the measures of satisfaction or dissatisfaction of decision-maker with offered alternative regarding defined criterion.

The sum of μ_I and ν_I does not have to be equal to 1 ($0 \leq \mu_I(x) + \nu_I(x) \leq 1, \forall x \in X$), because there is one more measure in HIFS, the so-called degree of hesitance or intuitionistic index or Atanassov's intuitionistic fuzzy index (Yao and Wang, 2018; Peng *et al*, 2015):

$$\pi_I(x) = 1 - \mu_I(x) - \nu_I(x),$$

where $0 \leq \pi_I(x) \leq 1$.

Figure 1 illustrates some possible situations regarding previously defined measures.

Figure 1. HIFS measures

Suppose that there are m alternatives $A = \{A_1, A_2, \dots, A_m\}$ and n criteria $C = \{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_n\}$. Initial matrix (where rows are alternatives and columns are criteria) for MCDM problem for discrete-valued HIFS measures can be defined as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} (\mu_{A_1}(x_1), \nu_{A_1}(x_1), \pi_{A_1}(x_1)) & (\mu_{A_1}(x_2), \nu_{A_1}(x_2), \pi_{A_1}(x_2)) & \dots & (\mu_{A_1}(x_n), \nu_{A_1}(x_n), \pi_{A_1}(x_n)) \\ (\mu_{A_2}(x_1), \nu_{A_2}(x_1), \pi_{A_2}(x_1)) & (\mu_{A_2}(x_2), \nu_{A_2}(x_2), \pi_{A_2}(x_2)) & \dots & (\mu_{A_2}(x_n), \nu_{A_2}(x_n), \pi_{A_2}(x_n)) \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ (\mu_{A_m}(x_1), \nu_{A_m}(x_1), \pi_{A_m}(x_1)) & (\mu_{A_m}(x_2), \nu_{A_m}(x_2), \pi_{A_m}(x_2)) & \dots & (\mu_{A_m}(x_n), \nu_{A_m}(x_n), \pi_{A_m}(x_n)) \end{bmatrix}$$

In a situation when the weight coefficients are not given and decision-maker chooses an alternative which satisfies either criteria C_1, C_2, \dots, C_{n-1} or the criterion C_n (this is one possible assumption, similarly it can be for a different combination of grouping the criteria regarding logical connectives „ \wedge “ and „ \vee “), the following evaluation function can be defined (Wang *et al*, 2006; Wang and Li, 2011):

$$E(A_i) = \langle \mu_i, \nu_i \rangle,$$

where, in this case, $\mu_i = \max(\min(\mu_{i1}, \mu_{i2}, \dots, \mu_{i(n-1)}), \mu_{in})$ and $\nu_i = \min(\max(\nu_{i1}, \nu_{i2}, \dots, \nu_{i(n-1)}), \nu_{in})$.

According to Ye (2009), if in Eq. (1) $p = \mu_i$ and $q = \frac{1}{2}(\mu_i + \nu_i)$, then $\frac{p}{q} = \frac{\mu_i}{\frac{1}{2}(\mu_i + \nu_i)} = \frac{2\mu_i}{\mu_i + \nu_i}$ and $\frac{1-p}{1-q} =$

$= \frac{1-\mu_i}{1-\frac{1}{2}(\mu_i + \nu_i)} = \frac{2(1-\mu_i)}{2-(\mu_i + \nu_i)}$, so, the following formula for cross-entropy can be obtained:

$$H(\mu_i, \nu_i) = \mu_i \log_2 \frac{2\mu_i}{\mu_i + \nu_i} + (1 - \mu_i) \log_2 \frac{2(1-\mu_i)}{2-(\mu_i + \nu_i)}, \quad 0 \leq \mu_i \leq 1. \quad (2)$$

In order to modify Eq. (2) to the symmetric form, the following calculation need to be done (Wang and Li, 2011):

$$H(E(A_i)) = (H(\mu_i, \nu_i) + H(\nu_i, \mu_i))/2.$$

The same authors suggest that the degree of suitability of alternative A_i with assumed decision-maker's requirement can be expressed by the following score function:

$$S(E(A_i)) = \begin{cases} \mu_i - \nu_i + H(E(A_i))\pi_i, & \mu_i > \nu_i \\ \mu_i - \nu_i - H(E(A_i))\pi_i, & \mu_i < \nu_i \\ 0, & \mu_i = \nu_i \end{cases}$$

The alternative with the highest score function is the best according to the defined requirement.

2.2. Cross-entropy for interval-valued HIFS in combination with extended TOPSIS

There are the lower (L) and the upper (U) points of the previously defined degrees of membership or belongingness in the case of an interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy set (Ye, 2011):

$$I = \{x, [\mu_l^l(x), \mu_l^u(x)], [\nu_l^l(x), \nu_l^u(x)] | x \in X\}.$$

Hesitant intuitionistic fuzzy interval index is:

$$\pi_l(x) = [1 - \mu_l^u(x) - \nu_l^u(x), 1 - \mu_l^l(x) - \nu_l^l(x)],$$

where $\mu_l^l(x) \geq 0, \nu_l^l(x) \geq 0, 0 \leq \mu_l^u(x) + \nu_l^u(x) \leq 1$.

After normalization of the initial matrix with m alternatives and n criteria, i.e. $([\mu_{ij}^l, \mu_{ij}^u], [\nu_{ij}^l, \nu_{ij}^u])_{m \times n}$, the normalized matrix can be transformed by using the following calculations for obtaining the lower and the upper bounds of its elements $([D_{ij}^l, D_{ij}^u])_{m \times n}$ (Zhang and Yu, 2012):

$$D_{ij}^L = \frac{\mu_{ij}^L \ln 2 + v_{ij}^U \ln \frac{2v_{ij}^U}{v_{ij}^L+1} + \ln \frac{2}{v_{ij}^L+1}}{(\mu_{ij}^L + v_{ij}^U) \ln 2 + \mu_{ij}^L \ln \frac{2\mu_{ij}^L}{\mu_{ij}^L+1} + v_{ij}^U \ln \frac{2v_{ij}^U}{v_{ij}^L+1} + \ln \frac{2}{\mu_{ij}^L+1} + \ln \frac{2}{v_{ij}^L+1}},$$

$$D_{ij}^U = \frac{\mu_{ij}^U \ln 2 + v_{ij}^L \ln \frac{2v_{ij}^L}{v_{ij}^U+1} + \ln \frac{2}{v_{ij}^U+1}}{(\mu_{ij}^U + v_{ij}^L) \ln 2 + \mu_{ij}^U \ln \frac{2\mu_{ij}^U}{\mu_{ij}^U+1} + v_{ij}^L \ln \frac{2v_{ij}^L}{v_{ij}^U+1} + \ln \frac{2}{\mu_{ij}^U+1} + \ln \frac{2}{v_{ij}^L+1}}. \quad (3)$$

The lower and the upper bounds also represent the minimum and the maximum of $D_{ij} = \frac{D_{ij}^-}{D_{ij}^+ + D_{ij}^-}$ (Tian *et al*, 2015), where D_{ij}^+ and D_{ij}^- represent degrees of discrimination of alternative A_i ($i = 1, \dots, m$) from positive ideal solution (A^+) and from negative ideal solution (A^-), respectively, regarding criterion C_j ($j = 1, \dots, n$).

In order to identify the optimal weight vector $\omega = (\omega_1, \omega_1, \dots, \omega_n)^T$, a mathematical model of linear programming, which includes the objective function $\max D = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n \omega_j \frac{D_{ij}^L + D_{ij}^U}{2}$ (Tian *et al*, 2015) and the given constraints (including natural constraints), need to be solved.

The preference of each alternative, $PREF_i = [PREF_i^L, PREF_i^U]$, can be computed by multiplying the optimal weight vector and the decision matrix $([D_{ij}^L, D_{ij}^U])_{m \times n}$ (Tian *et al*, 2015):

$$PREF_i = \sum_{j=1}^n \omega_j [D_{ij}^L, D_{ij}^U].$$

In the next step, the likelihood matrix (or pairwise comparison matrix) can be established as follows:

$$P = (p_{ij})_{m \times m} = \begin{bmatrix} p_{11} & p_{12} & \dots & p_{1m} \\ p_{21} & p_{22} & \dots & p_{2m} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ p_{m1} & p_{m2} & \dots & p_{mm} \end{bmatrix},$$

where according to Zhang and Yu (2012):

$$p_{ij} = p(A_i \geq A_j) = p(PREF_i \geq PREF_j) = \max \left\{ 1 - \max \left\{ \frac{PREF_j^U - PREF_i^L}{PREF_i^U - PREF_i^L + PREF_j^U - PREF_j^L}, 0 \right\}, 0 \right\}.$$

Note that the diagonal values of P equals 0.5, while $p_{ij} + p_{ji} = 1$ ($i = 1, \dots, m; j = 1, \dots, m$).

Finally, the ranking vector for the alternatives can be obtained as follows (Tian *et al*, 2015):

$$\omega_i = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^m p_{ij} + m/2 - 1}{m(m-1)}, i = 1, 2, \dots, m.$$

3. APPLICATION OF CROSS-ENTROPY FOR ROBOT SELECTION OPTIMIZATION

3.1. Selection of industrial robot – illustrative example 1

Selection of industrial robot is frequently described problem in the literature. In this example, we want to select one of three robots R_1, R_2, R_3 , intended for a computer integrated manufacturing system, regarding the following criteria: C_1 – adaptability, C_2 – flexibility, C_3 – capability (Haleh and Nezu, 2004). Initial matrix, where rows are alternatives and columns are criteria, is given in the form $(\mu_{ij}, \nu_{ij})_{3 \times 3}$, i.e. $(\mu_{ij}, \nu_{ij}, \pi_{ij})_{3 \times 3}$:

$$\begin{bmatrix} (0.45, 0.25) & (0.58, 0.15) & (0.4, 0.3) \\ (0.7, 0.12) & (0.6, 0.25) & (0.55, 0.1) \\ (0.65, 0.15) & (0.5, 0.4) & (0.4, 0.6) \end{bmatrix}, \text{ i.e. } \begin{bmatrix} (0.45, 0.25, 0.3) & (0.58, 0.15, 0.27) & (0.4, 0.3, 0.3) \\ (0.7, 0.12, 0.18) & (0.6, 0.25, 0.15) & (0.55, 0.1, 0.35) \\ (0.65, 0.15, 0.2) & (0.5, 0.4, 0.1) & (0.4, 0.6, 0.0) \end{bmatrix}.$$

According to the procedure described in Section 2.1 and the assumption that decision-maker wants to satisfy either criteria C_1 and C_2 or criterion C_3 , the results in Table 1 are obtained:

Table 1: Ranking the alternatives by the score function.

Alternative	$E(A_i)$	$H(E(A_i))$	$S(E(A_i))$
A_1	$\langle 0.45, 0.25 \rangle$	0.0320	0.2096
A_2	$\langle 0.6, 0.1 \rangle$	0.2141	0.5642
A_3	$\langle 0.5, 0.4 \rangle$	0.0073	0.1007

Therefore, the next order of the alternatives is adopted: $A_2 > A_1 > A_3$, so the alternative A_2 is the best.

3.2. Selection of education robot – illustrative example 2

“Robotics” course becomes widely represented in educational institutions (Parameshwaran *et al.*, 2015). In this illustrative example, we want to select one of three robots R_1, R_2, R_3 , intended for teaching purposes, regarding the following criteria: C_1 – possibilities of learning, C_2 – suitability of programming interface, C_3 – diversity of hardware performances, that we want to maximize. Initial matrix, where rows are alternatives and columns are criteria, is given in the form $([\mu_{ij}^L, \mu_{ij}^U], [v_{ij}^L, v_{ij}^U])_{3 \times 3}$:

$$\begin{bmatrix} ([0.6, 0.65], [0.15, 0.25]) & ([0.42, 0.49], [0.3, 0.5]) & ([0.65, 0.7], [0.3, 0.4]) \\ ([0.55, 0.62], [0.1, 0.3]) & ([0.3, 0.4], [0.6, 0.7]) & ([0.5, 0.7], [0.17, 0.23]) \\ ([0.75, 0.8], [0.5, 0.55]) & ([0.65, 0.8], [0.35, 0.4]) & ([0.4, 0.5], [0.4, 0.5]) \end{bmatrix}.$$

Partial information about the weight coefficients is given as follows: $0.2 \leq \omega_1 \leq 0.3$, $0.15 \leq \omega_2 \leq 0.25$, $0.3 \leq \omega_3 \leq 0.45$, $1.5\omega_1 \leq \omega_3$.

The initial matrix can be transformed by using Eq. (3) to the following form:

$$[D_{ij}^L, D_{ij}^U]_{3 \times 3} = \begin{bmatrix} [0.7458, 0.8502] & [0.4452, 0.6445] & [0.6496, 0.7447] \\ [0.6790, 0.8823] & [0.2553, 0.3740] & [0.7128, 0.8489] \\ [0.5949, 0.6413] & [0.6496, 0.7388] & [0.4304, 0.5696] \end{bmatrix}.$$

Based on that, the following mathematical model (M_1) can be defined in order to find optimal value:

$$\max D = 2.1967\omega_1 + 1.5537\omega_2 + 1.9780\omega_3$$

s.t. $\omega_1 \geq 0$, $\omega_2 \geq 0$, $\omega_3 \geq 0$,

$$\omega_1 \geq 0.2, \omega_1 \leq 0.3, \omega_2 \geq 0.15, \omega_2 \leq 0.25, \omega_3 \geq 0.3, \omega_3 \leq 0.45, 1.5\omega_1 \leq \omega_3,$$

$$\omega_1 + \omega_2 + \omega_3 = 1.$$

The optimal value is obtained by solving M_1 in Lingo software: $\omega = (0.30, 0.25, 0.45)^T$.

According to the procedure described in Section 2.2, calculation of the preference is done for each alternative: $PREF_1 = [0.6274, 0.7513]$, $PREF_2 = [0.5883, 0.7402]$, $PREF_3 = [0.5345, 0.6334]$.

The next step is the calculation of the likelihood matrix based on the obtained preferences:

$$P = (p_{ij})_{3 \times 3} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.5 & 0.5910 & 0.9731 \\ 0.4090 & 0.5 & 0.8202 \\ 0.0269 & 0.1798 & 0.5 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Finally, we can calculate the ranking vector of all alternatives: $\omega_1 = 0.4273$, $\omega_2 = 0.3715$, $\omega_3 = 0.2011$. Therefore, the next order of the alternatives is adopted: $A_1 > A_2 > A_3$, so the alternative A_1 is the best.

4. CONCLUSION

Cross-entropy based MCDM approach for robot selection is suggested to be used in an uncertain HIFS environment that engineers face due to incomplete information and complex tasks, which is why they are hesitant when voting. It is possible to use it successfully in different situations depending on how the input data are defined, for both discrete-valued HIFS and interval-valued HIFS. The results of illustrative examples show unambiguous sorted alternatives despite initial vagueness. Sensitive results are obtained, and therefore, there are not “equally good” alternatives. All partial input information is used in order to rank the alternatives. The approach considers the human intuitive nature and it is suitable for decision-making in socio-technical environment.

The use of cross-entropy in combination with other MCDM methods and comparison of the results is also possible but is not described in this paper. Deeper learning based on cross-entropy to overcome intuitive factors in a very demanding and responsible area such as robotics remains for future research.

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